

Table 1. Competency Questions and Results from OntoCaimer (SPARQL).

#	Question	SPARQL Query	Result
1	What exercises can I do with patient Joe?	<pre> SELECT ?examples WHERE { ?patient a c:Patient. ?patient c:hasFullName"Joe"^^xsd:string. ?patient c:suffers ?sin. ?sin a ?res. ?res rdfs:subClassOf ?prop. ?prop owl:onProperty c:belongsTo. ?prop owl:hasValue ?stage. ?rec c:Examples ?examples. BIND (IF (?stage = c:Moderate, c:RMI14, IF (?stage = c:Mild, c:RMI14, IF(?stage=c:Severe, c:RS44,"))) AS ?filterTerm) FILTER(?rec = ?filterTerm) } </pre>	<p>"Stand up and move about regularly, Sit unsupported for a few minutes each day, Lie as flat as possible on the bed for 20-30 minutes each day, Balance in a standing position, In the sitting position shuffle along the edge of the bed from one end of the bed to the other"</p>
2	What recommendations have examples?	<pre> SELECT ?rec WHERE { ?rec c:Examples ?examples } </pre>	<p> http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RS23 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RS33 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI17 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI8 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMO18 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RS16 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMO12 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI3 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI6 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMO14 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI4 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMO23 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RS45 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI18 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RS52 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RS4 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI16 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI2 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI1 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RS44 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI9 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI15 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RS40 http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RMI7 </p>

			http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/RS54
3	What activities does patient Joe have on his agenda?	<pre>SELECT ?act WHERE { ?patient a c:Patient. ?patient c:hasFullName "Joe"^^xsd:string. ?patient c:does ?act. }</pre>	http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Breakfast http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Dinner http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Lunch http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Sleep
4	What time should patient Joe have lunch?	<pre>SELECT ?hour WHERE { ?patient a c:Patient. ?patient c:hasFullName "Joe"^^xsd:string. c:Lunch c:hasStartTime ?hour. }</pre>	"12:00:00"^^< http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#time >
5	An activity starting at 9pm by Patient Joe	<pre>SELECT ?act WHERE { ?patient a c:Patient. ?patient c:hasFullName "Joe"^^xsd:string. ?patient c:does ?act. ?act c:hasStartTime "21:00:00"^^xsd:time. }</pre>	http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Sleep
6	What is patient Mary Bet's most recent symptom?	<pre>SELECT ?type WHERE { ?patient a c:Patient. ?patient c:hasFullName "Mary Bet"^^xsd:string. ?patient c:suffers ?sin. ?sin c:hasStartDay ?period. ?sin a ?type. ?type rdfs:subClassOf c:Symptom. } ORDER BY DESC (?period) LIMIT 1</pre>	http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Delusion_and_paranoidia
7	What are Patient Joe's symptoms?	<pre>SELECT DISTINCT ?re WHERE { ?patient a c:Patient. ?patient c:hasFullName "Joe"^^xsd:string. ?patient c:suffers ?sin. ?sin a ?re. ?re rdfs:subClassOf c:Symptom } ORDER BY (?re)</pre>	http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Weight_loss

8	What are patient Joe's recommendations?	<pre>SELECT ?re WHERE { ?patient a c:Patient. ?patient c:hasFullName "Joe"^^xsd:string. ?patient c:suffers ?sin. ?sin c:hasRecommendation ?rec. ?rec c:DescriptionRecommendation ?re. }</pre>	<p>The eating area should be quiet and calm^^xsd:string Ensure patient's dentures are properly fitted^^xsd:string Avoid food out of schedule^^xsd:string Serve meals at the same time^^xsd:string The patient's weight should not lose less than 5kg monthly^^xsd:string</p>
9	What are the weight loss recommendations?	<pre>SELECT ?res ?de WHERE{c:Seizure rdfs:subClassOf ?re. ?re owl:onProperty c:hasRecommendation. ?re owl:hasValue ?res. ?res c:DescriptionRecommendation ?de. }</pre>	<p>"Keep the patient safe and comfort" "Call a service emergency if the patient is injured or the seizure lasts more than two minutes" "Move any heave or sharp objects out of the way" "Lay the patient on their side" "Place something soft under the patient's head" "Remove glasses"</p>
10	Who takes care of patient Joe?	<pre>SELECT ?name WHERE { ?s a c:Patient. ?s c:isCaredBy ?care. ?s c:hasFullName "Joe"^^xsd:string. ?care c:hasFullName ?name }</pre>	<p>"Antony"</p>
11	Is patient Joe's weight appropriate?	<pre>SELECT ?healthy WHERE{ ?patient rdf:type c:Patient. ?patient c:hasFullName "Joe"^^xsd:string. ?patient c:hasWeight ?weight. ?patient sosa:isFeatureOfInterestOf ?obs. ?obs sosa:madeBySensor c:WeighingMachine. ?obs sosa:hasResult ?res. ?res qudt:numericValue ?value. BIND((?weight-5) <?value AS ?healthy). }</pre>	<p>"false"^^<http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#boolean></p>

12	What is the condition of the dining room?	<pre> SELECT ?result WHERE { ?room a c:Room. ?room c:TypeOfRoom "Dining room". ?room c:state ?result } </pre>	Calm and Silence^^xsd:string
13	What are the symptoms of the severe stage?	<pre> SELECT ?sin WHERE{ ?sin rdfs:subClassOf c:Symptom. ?sin rdfs:subClassOf ?res. ?res owl:onProperty c:belongsTo. ?res owl:hasValue c:Severe } </pre>	http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Lack_of_control_of_bowel_and_bladder http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Inability_to_communicate http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Inability_to_recognize_oneself_or_family http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Increased_sleeping http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Groaning_moaning_or_grunting http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Difficult_to_walk_or_sit http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Weight_loss http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Seizure http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Difficulty_swallowing http://www.semanticweb.org/OntoCaimer/Skin_infection
14	What sensors does the dining room have?	<pre> SELECT ?sensor WHERE { ?room a c:Room. ?room c:TypeOfRoom "Dining room"^^xsd:string. ?room sosa:hosts ?sensor . ?sensor a sosa:Sensor. } </pre>	c:NoiseSensor
15	How much noise is there in the dining room?	<pre> SELECT ?value WHERE{ ?room a c:Room. ?room c:TypeOfRoom "Dining room". ?room sosa:isFeatureOfInterestOf ?obs. ?obs sosa:madeBySensor c:NoiseSensor. ?obs sosa:hasResult ?res. ?res qudt:numericValue ?value. } </pre>	"54"^^< http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer >

16	What is the noise level in the dining room?	<pre> SELECT ?result WHERE { ?room a c:Room. ?room c:TypeOfRoom "Dining room". ?room c:state ?result. } </pre>	Calm and Silence^^xsd:string
17	What activities can I do with patient Mary?	<pre> SELECT DISTINCT ?examples WHERE { ?patient a c:Patient. ?patient c:hasFullName "Mary Bet"^^xsd:string. ?patient c:suffers ?sin. ?sin a ?res. ?res rdfs:subClassOf ?prop. ?prop owl:onProperty c:belongsTo. ?prop owl:hasValue ?stage. ?rec c:Examples ?examples. BIND(IF(?stage = c:Moderate, c:RMI7, c:RMO12) AS ?filterTerm) FILTER(?rec = ?filterTerm) } </pre>	<p>"Reading books, newspapers or magazines or audio books or podcasts. Visiting friends or family members. Looking at old photographs or souvenirs from past events. Cooking together. Puzzles. Flower arranging. Listening to favorite music."</p>